

***PASILIP SA LUSOG-ISIP: USER SATISFACTION AND CONTENT
REVIEW OF MENTAL HEALTH MOBILE APP AMONG
PSYCHOLOGY STUDENTS OF MALAYAN COLLEGES
LAGUNA AS BASIS FOR MENTAL HEALTH
APP CONTENT DEVELOPMENT***

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Pasilip sa Lusog-Isip: User Satisfaction and Content Review of Mental Health Mobile App Among Psychology Students of Malayan Colleges Laguna as Basis for Mental Health App Content Development

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Abstract

This study explored and identified the user satisfaction and content review of Psychology students of Mapua Malayan Colleges Laguna of the first culturally adapted mental health app in the Philippines, Lusog-Isip. Then, as a basis for the content development of the app and other mental health mobile apps, the results of this study will be used. This study used an exploratory mixed-method research design to identify the user satisfaction level of psychology students. Then, the researchers chose ten random psychology students from different year levels (1st-3rd year) to examine their perception regarding the contents of the Lusog-Isip mental health app. The statistical analysis indicated varied user satisfaction while utilizing and navigating the app. Most outcomes indicated overall satisfaction among numerous students, with only a minority expressing dissatisfaction. Nevertheless, certain features received criticism and requests for enhancement. Participants offered valuable qualitative insights on the content of the Lusog-Isip app, leading to notable recommendations. The selected participants suggest specific improvements and refinements for the ongoing development of the Lusog-Isip app. As stated, Mental health professionals affiliated with MMCL have confirmed the validity of the proposed content for the mental health app.

Keywords: *mental health, mobile apps, pandemic, telehealth, user satisfaction, content review, content development*

Introduction

As stated by the World Health Organization [WHO] (2022), mental health is essential for socioeconomic, societal, and personal development, and people suffering from mental illnesses are more likely to have poorer levels of mental well-being. Recent studies showed that mental health during the pandemic, the number of individuals with anxiety and depression, and other mental health illnesses increased (WHO, 2022). In the surge of the pandemic, the enthusiasm, interest, and acceptance of using technology for mental health care were seen as an opportunity by mental health professionals (Wind et al., 2020, as cited by Torous et al., 2020). With people being more reliant on their gadgets nowadays, most mental health applications were built to be based on traditional psychotherapy procedures, especially when the COVID-19 pandemic has brought attention to the role of telehealth and technological resources like apps for mental health and providing care. Maravilla and Tan (2021) stated that mental disorders are nonexistent in the Philippines. That being said, mental health services were never a high priority until the Department of Health [DOH] (n.d.) established a strategic plan for mental health that affirms the basic rights of those in need of mental health services. Self-care interventions are becoming more common and less stigmatized. As a result, a mobile mental health application called “Lusog-Isip” was collaboratively launched by the Department of Health and USAID Philippines.

This study aimed to measure the user satisfaction levels and evaluate the perceptions of Mapua Malayan Colleges Laguna (MMCL) Psychology Major students regarding the features and content of the Lusog-Isip mental health app. Specific questions addressed include evaluating the app's features, user satisfaction levels, the impact of app strengths and weaknesses on user satisfaction, participant perceptions, and potential contributions to future mental health app development. The main purpose of this study is to quantitatively and qualitatively assess the viewpoint of MMCL Psychology Major students on the Lusog-Isip mental health app. Specific objectives include evaluating app features, determining user satisfaction levels, overall satisfaction rates, and participant perceptions, and providing recommendations for future app development. In a broader context, this study contributes to our understanding of mental health in the Philippines by highlighting the rapid changes created by digital platforms. The study's results have practical significance for various groups beyond academic implications. Psychology majors and other students can use the results as a guide for selecting mental health apps tailored to coping mechanisms and promoting healthier stress management. Mental health practitioners can benefit from insights into client conditions by utilizing improved app content to monitor and evaluate mental health conditions effectively. The study also offers a foundation for app developers, which can aid in enhancing mental health app features and content. Insights from this study can guide mental health mobile app developers in enhancing interface design, content, and features. The improved mental health app offers convenient and free access to mental health resources and services through mobile phones for the general public. Lastly, future researchers can use this study as a reference and foundational model for exploring similar topics of interest.

Methodology

Research Design

The study applied an explanatory mixed method as its research design to employ both quantitative, which is the level of user satisfaction using a 4-point Likert scale, and qualitative data, the content review and insights from ten randomly selected psychology students from

Mapua Malayan Colleges Laguna (MMCL).

Respondents

This study's participants focused solely on the psychology students of Mapua Malayan Colleges Laguna, from all year levels, from the school year 2022-2023, 3rd term. Using non-probability sampling techniques, specifically purposive and quota sampling — as the respondents. Using Slovin's formula, the three-year levels (strata) sample sizes were calculated and determined based on the overall population size of psychology students per demographic group. Based on the calculations, 90 is the overall sample size of the study. Then, out of 90, 10 students were randomly selected for an interview.

Ethical Considerations

In accordance with the Data Privacy Act of 2012, this study meticulously adhered to legal guidelines, prioritizing the utmost confidentiality and privacy of the participants. The participants were thoroughly informed about the study's objectives, methodologies, and the specific use of their personal information, providing explicit informed consent. The research guarantees that all personal information collected from participants was utilized exclusively for the stated purposes and will be securely stored with strict measures to prevent unauthorized access.

Results and Discussion

User Satisfaction Level of the respondents.

Table 1. *User Satisfaction of Psychology Students per Year Level Based on the Accuracy of Information of Lusog-Isip App*

Year	Dissatisfied	Satisfied	Very Satisfied	Total
First	0	20	10	30
Second	1	16	10	27
Third	0	25	8	33
Total	1	61	38	90

Note. 'Accuracy' Satisfaction Level gathered by the authors on April 2023.

Based on the responses, 61 students, 20 from 1st-year, 16 from 2nd-year, and 25 from 3rd-year students, were satisfied with the accuracy of information and content of the Lusog-Isip app. While 28 students, 10 from 1st and 2nd-year, and 8 from 3rd-year, stated they were very satisfied with the app's content accuracy, one from 2nd-year voted dissatisfied.

Table 2. *User Satisfaction of Psychology Students per Year Level Based on the Relevance of Information of Lusog-Isip App*

Year	Dissatisfied	Satisfied	Very Satisfied	Total
First	1	19	10	30
Second	0	18	0	27
Third	1	20	12	33
Total	2	57	31	90

Note. 'Relevance' Satisfaction Level gathered by the authors on April 2023.

57 students in total agreed that the topics included in the Lusog-Isip app are relevant and satisfying. 19 first-year, 18 second-year, and 21 third-year students expressed their willingness to be satisfied. On the other hand, 37 students—10 from first year, 9 from second year, and 12 from third year—said they were very satisfied. Only two students—one from each of the first and third years—felt that the content of Lusog-Isip was irrelevant.

Table 3. *User Satisfaction of Psychology Students per Year Level on How Empirical Based the Information in Lusog-Isip*

Year	Dissatisfied	Satisfied	Very Satisfied	Total
First	1	16	13	30
Second	1	17	9	27
Third	2	18	13	33
Total	4	51	35	90

Note. 'Empirical Based' Satisfaction Level gathered by the authors on April 2023.

The number of satisfied students was 51, 16 from 1st-year, 17 from 2nd-year, and 18 from 3rd-year. This was followed by 35, 13 students from 1st-year, 9 from 2nd-year, and 13 from 3rd-year, who stated that they were very satisfied with how the information of Lusog-Isip was empirically based. However, four students disagreed and voted dissatisfied.

Out of 90 students, 48 were satisfied, 16 students from each year level. Forty-one students were very satisfied, 14 from 1st-year, 11 from 2nd-year, and 16 from 3rd-year. Additionally, only one was dissatisfied with the credibility of the information and sources of the app.

Table 4. *User Satisfaction of Psychology Students per Year Level Based on the Credibility of Information in Lusog-Isip App*

Year	Dissatisfied	Satisfied	Very Satisfied	Total
First	0	16	14	30
Second	0	16	11	27
Third	1	16	16	33
Total	1	48	41	90

Note. 'Credibility' Satisfaction Level gathered by the authors on April 2023.

Table 5. *User Satisfaction of Psychology Students per Year Level Based on the Concision of Information in Lusog-Isip App*

Year	Dissatisfied	Satisfied	Very Satisfied	Total
First	5	18	7	30
Second	3	16	8	27
Third	8	17	8	33
Total	15	51	23	90

Note. 'Concision' Satisfaction Level gathered by the authors on April 2023.

The Concision of the Lusog-Isip app, according to the Psychology students, 51 of them were satisfied, 18 students from the 1st-year, 16 from the 2nd-year, and 17 from the 3rd-year level. Alongside, 23 students were very satisfied, 7 from the 1st-year level and 8 from the 2nd-year and 3rd-year levels. Lastly, a total of 16 students, 5 from the 1st year, 3 from the 2nd year, and 8 from the 3rd-year level, were dissatisfied.

Table 6. *User Satisfaction of Psychology Students per Year Level Based on the Contextual Adaptability of Information in Lusog-Isip App*

Year	Very Dissatisfied	Dissatisfied	Satisfied	Very Satisfied	Total
First	1	4	19	9	30
Second	0	2	18	10	27
Third	0	5	20	9	33
Total	1	11	50	28	90

Note. 'Conceptual Adaptability' Satisfaction Level gathered by the authors on April 2023.

There were 50 Psychology students, 16 from 1st-year level, 15 from 2nd-year, and 19 from 3rd-year, who agreed that the Contextual Adaptability of Lusog-Isip was satisfying. Moreover, a total of 28 students, 9 from the 1st-year level, 10 from the 2nd-year, and 9 from the 3rd-year, reported they were very satisfied. However, 11 students voted dissatisfied, with one student who was very dissatisfied with Lusog-Isip's Contextual Adaptability.

Table 6. *User Satisfaction of Psychology Students Based on the User Friendliness of the Lusog-Isip App*

Year	Dissatisfied	Satisfied	Very Satisfied	Total
First	4	11	15	30
Second	3	15	9	27
Third	0	21	12	33
Total	7	47	36	90

Note. 'Relevance' Satisfaction Level gathered by the authors on April 2023.

In total, 47 students agreed to be satisfied with the user-friendliness of the Lusog-Isip app. Students who agreed to be satisfied were 11 students from 1st-year, 15 from 2nd-year, and 21 from 3rd-year. Thirty-six students, 15 from 1st-year, 9 from 2nd-year, and 12 from 3rd-year, on the other hand, stated they were very satisfied. Meanwhile, seven students, 4 from 1st-year and 3 from 2nd-year, felt dissatisfied with Lusog-Isip's user-friendliness.

Table 7. *User Satisfaction of Psychology Students Based on the Comprehensibility of the Lusog-Isip App*

Year	Dissatisfied	Satisfied	Very Satisfied	Total
First	1	19	10	30
Second	2	17	8	27
Third	3	17	13	33
Total	6	53	31	90

Note. 'Comprehensibility' Satisfaction Level gathered by the authors on April 2023.

There were 53 Psychology students, 19 from 1st-year level, 17 from 2nd-year, and 17 from 3rd-year, who agreed that the Comprehensibility of Lusog-Isip was satisfying. Moreover, a total of 31 students, 10 from the 1st-year level, 8 from the 2nd-year, and 13 from the 3rd year reported they were very satisfied. However, 6 students, one from 1st-year, two from 2nd-year, and three from 3rd-year, voted dissatisfied with Lusog-Isip's Comprehensibility.

Table 8. *User Satisfaction of Psychology Students Based on the Functionality of Lusog-Isip App*

Year	Very Dissatisfied	Dissatisfied	Satisfied	Very Satisfied	Total
First	1	3	17	9	30
Second	1	3	14	9	27
Third	2	3	20	8	33
Total	4	9	51	26	90

Note. 'Functionality' Satisfaction Level gathered by the authors on April 2023.

51 students, 17 from 1st-year, 14 from 2nd-year, and 20 from 3rd-year students, were satisfied with the functionality of the Lusog-Isip app. Meanwhile, 26 students, 9 from 1st and 2nd-year, and 8 from 3rd-year, stated they were very satisfied with the app's functionality. In addition, 9 students voted dissatisfied, while a total of 4 were very dissatisfied.

Table 9. *User Satisfaction of Psychology Students Based on the Performance of the Lusog-Isip App*

Year	Very Dissatisfied	Dissatisfied	Satisfied	Very Satisfied	Total
First	3	6	11	10	30
Second	1	8	10	8	27

Note. 'Performance' Satisfaction Level gathered by the authors on April 2023.

Out of 90 students, 36 were satisfied, 11 students from 1st-year, 10 from 2nd-year, and 15 from 3rd-year level. Twenty-two students were very satisfied, 10 from 1st-year, 8 from 2nd-year, and 4 from 3rd-year. Additionally, 26 students were dissatisfied, and 6 were very dissatisfied with the app's performance.

Table 10. *User Satisfaction of Psychology Students Based on the Navigation of Lusog-Isip App*

Year	Dissatisfied	Satisfied	Very Satisfied	Total
First	4	17	9	30
Second	3	18	6	27
Third	3	21	9	33
Total	10	56	24	90

Note. 'Navigation' Satisfaction Level gathered by the authors on April 2023

The number of satisfied students was 56: 17 students from 1st-year, 18 from 2nd-year, and 21 from 3rd-year. Followed by twenty-four, 9 students from 1st-year, 6 from 2nd-year, and 9 from 3rd-year, who stated that they were very satisfied with the navigation of Lusog-Isip. However, ten students disagreed and voted dissatisfied.

Table 11. *User Satisfaction of Psychology Students Based on the Usability of Lusog-Isip App*

Year	Very Dissatisfied	Dissatisfied	Satisfied	Very Satisfied	Total
First	1	1	19	9	30
Second	0	4	16	7	27
Third	0	2	22	9	33
Total	1	7	57	25	90

Note. 'Usability' Satisfaction Level gathered by the authors on April 2023

Regarding the usability of the Lusog-Isip app, according to the Psychology students, 57 were satisfied, 19 were from 1st-year, 16 from 2nd-year, and 22 from 3rd-year level. Alongside, 25 students were very satisfied, 9 students from the 1st-year level, 7 from the 2nd-year, and 9 from the 3rd-year. A total of 7 students, one from 1st-year, 4 from 2nd-year, and 2 from the 3rd-year level, were dissatisfied, while only one student was very dissatisfied.

Table 12. *User Satisfaction of Psychology Students Based on the Accessibility of Lusog-Isip App*

Year	Very Dissatisfied	Dissatisfied	Satisfied	Very Satisfied	Total
First	0	3	18	9	30
Second	1	5	16	5	27
Third	2	6	17	8	33
Total	3	14	51	22	90

Note. 'Accessibility' Satisfaction Level gathered by the authors on April 2023.

51 students agreed to be satisfied with the accessibility of the Lusog-Isip app. Students who agreed to be satisfied were 18 students from 1st-year, 16 from 2nd-year, and 17 from 3rd-year. 22 students, 9 from 1st-year, 5 from 2nd-year, and 8 from 3rd-year stated they were very satisfied. Meanwhile, 14 students, 3 from 1st-year, 5 from 2nd-year, and 6 from 3rd-year, felt dissatisfied with Lusog-Isip's accessibility. Lastly, 3 students were very dissatisfied.

Table 13. *User Satisfaction of Psychology Students Based on the Customisation of Lusog-Isip App*

Year	Very Dissatisfied	Dissatisfied	Satisfied	Very Satisfied	Total
First	1	3	19	7	30
Second	0	5	15	7	27
Third	0	1	23	9	33
Total	1	9	57	23	90

Note. 'Customisation' Satisfaction Level gathered by the authors on April 2023.

Out of 90 students, 57 were satisfied, 19 students from 1st-year, 15 from 2nd-year, and 23 from 3rd-year. Also, 23 students were very satisfied, 7 from 1st-year, 7 from 2nd-year, and 9 from 3rd-year. Additionally, 9 were dissatisfied, and only one was very dissatisfied with the app's customisation.

Table 14. *User Satisfaction of Psychology Students Based on the Entertainment Features of Lusog-Isip App*

Year	Very Dissatisfied	Dissatisfied	Satisfied	Very Satisfied	Total
First	1	4	19	6	30
Second	0	4	18	5	27
Third	0	9	17	9	33
Total	1	17	54	18	90

Note. 'Entertainment' Satisfaction Level gathered by the authors on April 2023.

54 psychology students—19 from the first year, 18 from the second year, and 17 from the third year reported being satisfied with the Lusog-Isip app's entertainment features. 18 students overall, including 6 first-year students, 5 second-year students, and 7 third-year students, were very satisfied. In total, 17 students—4 from the first year, 4 from the second year, and 9 from the third year were dissatisfied, but just one student was very dissatisfied.

Table 15. *User Satisfaction of Psychology Students Based on Their Interest in the Lusog-Isip App*

Year	Dissatisfied	Satisfied	Very Satisfied	Total
First	3	16	11	30
Second	3	17	7	27
Third	4	17	12	33
Total	10	50	30	90

Note. 'Interest' Satisfaction Level gathered by the authors on April 2023

Out of 90 students, 50 were satisfied, including 16 first-year students, 17 second-year students, and 17 third-year students. Additionally, 30 students—11 from first-year, 7 from second-year, and 12 from third-year were very satisfied. Furthermore, 10 students were dissatisfied.

Table 16. *User Satisfaction of Psychology Students Based on the Interactivity of Lusog-Isip App*

Year	Very Dissatisfied	Dissatisfied	Satisfied	Very Satisfied	Total
First	1	0	22	7	30
Second	0	1	19	7	27
Third	1	4	19	9	33
Total	2	5	60	23	90

Note. 'Interactivity' Satisfaction Level gathered by the authors on April 2023.

The Interactivity of Lusog-Isip was voted as satisfying by 60 psychology students, including 22 from the first-year level, 19 from the second year, and 19 from the third year. Additionally, a total of 23 students, including 7 from the first-year level, 7 from the second year, and 9 from the third year, said they were very satisfied. However, 5 students were dissatisfied, and two were very dissatisfied with Lusog-Isip's interactivity.

Table 17. *User Satisfaction of Psychology Students Based on the Logo of Lusog-Isip App*

Year	Dissatisfied	Satisfied	Very Satisfied	Total
First	1	14	15	30
Second	1	17	9	27
Third	3	16	14	33
Total	5	47	38	90

Note. 'Logo' Satisfaction Level gathered by the authors on April 2023.

There were 47 Psychology students, 14 from 1st-year level, 17 from 2nd-year, and 16 from 3rd-year, who agreed that the Logo of Lusog-Isip was satisfying. Moreover, a total of 38 students, 15 from the 1st-year level, 9 from the 2nd-year, and 14 from the 3rd-year reported they were very satisfied. However, there were 5 students, one from 1st-year, one from 2nd-year, and three from 3rd-year, who voted dissatisfied with Lusog-Isip's logo.

Table 18. *User Satisfaction of Psychology Students Based on the Layout of Lusog-Isip App*

Year	Dissatisfied	Satisfied	Very Satisfied	Total
First	1	20	9	30
Second	2	17	8	27
Third	2	18	13	33
Total	5	55	30	90

Note. 'Layout' Satisfaction Level gathered by the authors on April 2023.

Regarding the layout of the Lusog-Isip app, of the Psychology students 55 were satisfied, 20 students from 1st-year, 17 from the 2nd-year, and 18 from the 3rd-year level. Alongside, 30 students were very satisfied, 9 students from the 1st-year level, 8 from the 2nd-

year, and 13 from the 3rd-year. A total of 5 students, one from 1st-year, two from 2nd-year, and two from the 3rd-year level, were dissatisfied.

Table 19. *User Satisfaction of Psychology Students Based on the Graphics of Lusog-Isip App*

Year	Dissatisfied	Satisfied	Very Satisfied	Total
First	1	18	11	30
Second	2	17	8	27
Third	4	18	11	33
Total	7	53	30	90

Note. 'Graphics' Satisfaction Level gathered by the authors on April 2023.

The number of satisfied students was 53: 18 students from 1st-year, 17 from 2nd-year, and 18 from 3rd-year. Followed by 30, 11 students from 1st-year, 8 from 2nd-year, and 11 from 3rd-year, who stated that they were very satisfied with the graphics of Lusog-Isip. However, 7 students disagreed and voted dissatisfied.

Table 20. *User Satisfaction of Psychology Students Based on the Visual Appeal of Lusog-Isip App*

Year	Very Dissatisfied	Dissatisfied	Satisfied	Very Satisfied	Total
First	0	3	17	10	30
Second	0	7	13	7	27
Third	1	7	18	7	33
Total	1	17	48	24	90

Note. 'Visual Appeal' Satisfaction Level gathered by the authors on April 2023.

Based on the responses of the Psychology students, 48 students, 17 from 1st-year, 13 from 2nd-year, and 18 from 3rd-year students, were satisfied with the visual appeal of the Lusog-Isip app. While 24 students, 10 from 1st-year, 7 from 2nd-year, and 7 from 3rd-year, stated they were very satisfied with the app's visual appeal. Seventeen 2nd-year students voted dissatisfied, while only one voted very dissatisfied.

Table 21. *User Satisfaction of Psychology Students Based on the Style Consistency of Lusog-Isip App*

Year	Dissatisfied	Satisfied	Very Satisfied	Total
First	1	15	14	30
Second	3	15	9	27
Third	2	18	13	33
Total	6	48	36	90

Note. 'Style Consistency' Satisfaction Level gathered by the authors on April 2023.

In total, 48 students were satisfied with the style consistency of the Lusog-Isip app. Students who voted satisfied were 15 students from 1st-year, 15 from 2nd-year, and 18 from 3rd-year. Thirty-six students, 14 from 1st-year, 9 from 2nd-year, and 13 from 3rd-year, on the other hand, stated they were very satisfied. Lastly, six students, one from 1st-year, three from 2nd-year, and two from 3rd-year, were dissatisfied with Lusog-Isip's style consistency.

Table 22. *User Satisfaction of Psychology Students Based on the Color Scheme of Lusog-Isip App*

Year	Dissatisfied	Satisfied	Very Satisfied	Total
First	1	17	12	30
Second	2	17	8	27
Third	2	16	15	33
Total	5	50	35	90

Note. 'Color Scheme' Satisfaction Level gathered by the authors on April 2023.

The colour scheme of Lusog-Isip was voted as satisfying by 50 psychology students, including 17 from the first-year level, 17 from the second year, and 16 from the third year. Furthermore, a total of 35 students, including 12 from the first-year level, 8 from the second year, and 15 from the third year, said they were very satisfied. However, 5 students were dissatisfied with the Lusog-Isip app's colour scheme.

Table 23. *User Satisfaction of Psychology Students Based on the Data Security of Lusog-Isip App*

Year	Very Dissatisfied	Dissatisfied	Satisfied	Very Satisfied	Total
First	0	0	15	15	30
Second	0	0	13	14	27
Third	1	1	15	16	33
Total	1	1	43	45	90

Note. 'Data Security' Satisfaction Level gathered by the authors on April 2023.

43 psychology students, with 15 from the first-year level, 13 from the second year, and 15 from the third year, voted that the data security of the Lusog-Isip app was satisfying. To add, total of 45 students, including 15 first-year students, 14 second-year students,

and 16 third-year students, stated they were very satisfied. However, the data security of the Lusog-Isip app dissatisfied only one student, and another one was very dissatisfied.

Table 24. *User Satisfaction of Psychology Students Based on the Data Privacy of Lusog-Isip App*

Year	Dissatisfied	Satisfied	Very Satisfied	Total
First	0	12	18	30
Second	0	14	13	27
Third	2	17	14	33
Total	2	43	45	90

Note. 'Data Privacy' Satisfaction Level gathered by the authors on April 2023.

The number of satisfied students was 43: 12 students from 1st-year, 14 from 2nd-year, and 17 from 3rd-year. Followed by 45, 18 students from 1st-year, 13 from 2nd-year, and 14 from 3rd-year, who stated that they were very satisfied with the data privacy of Lusog-Isip. However, only 2 students disagreed and voted dissatisfied.

Table 25. *User Satisfaction of Psychology Students Based on the Availability of Lusog-Isip App*

Year	Dissatisfied	Satisfied	Very Satisfied	Total
First	0	10	20	30
Second	1	5	21	27
Third	2	10	21	33
Total	9	60	21	90

Note. 'Availability' Satisfaction Level gathered by the authors on April 2023.

Regarding the availability of the Lusog-Isip app, according to the Psychology students, 25 were satisfied, 10 were from the 1st-year, 5 from the 2nd-year, and 10 from the 3rd-year level. Also, 62 students were very satisfied, 20 students from the 1st-year level, 21 from the 2nd-year, and 21 from the 3rd-year. A total of 3 students, only 1 from the 2nd-year and two from the 3rd-year level, were dissatisfied.

Table 26. *Overall User Satisfaction of Psychology Students on Lusog-Isip App*

Year	Dissatisfied	Satisfied	Very Satisfied	Total
First	3	22	5	30
Second	4	15	8	27
Third	2	23	8	33
Total	9	60	21	90

Note. 'Overall' Satisfaction Level gathered by the authors on April 2023.

Of 90 students, 60 were satisfied, including 22 first-year students, 15 second-year students, and 23 third-year students. In addition, 21 students—5 from first-year, 8 from second-year, and 8 from third-year were very satisfied. Furthermore, 9 students were dissatisfied with the overall Lusog-Isip app.

The Overall Satisfaction Rate of the Psychology Students

Table 27. *Satisfaction Rate of the Psychology Students*

	Dissatisfied	Satisfied	Very Satisfied	Total
Number of answers	9	60	21	90

The calculated satisfaction rate of 90%, based on the number of very satisfied and satisfied responses among a total of 90 respondents, signifies a substantial and positive level of satisfaction among Psychology students. This result indicates a high overall satisfaction rate in the collected data, showing that most psychology students are either satisfied or very satisfied.

Based on the UK Customer Satisfaction Index of July 2021, the acceptable and good satisfaction rate of good quality services, specifically for leisure (mobile applications, social media, online streaming platforms, etc.), is 80.7% and above. Therefore, this suggests that the overall satisfaction level of the Psychology students from Mapúa Malayan Colleges Laguna of the Lusog-Isip mental health app, is good.

This result is consistently in line with the findings of Hechanova-Alampay et al. (2022) regarding the pilot evaluation and development of the Lusog-Isip app wherein 85.9% of Filipino participants expressed satisfaction, yielding an overall mean score of 53.1 determined by the Healthcare Smartphone App Evaluation Tool (HSAET).

Lusog-Isip app has garnered positive feedback from the majority for its helpful and enjoyable experience. Thus, signifying a favorable support to Hechanova-Alampay et al. (2022)'s research insights which report a notable improvement in terms of interpersonal skills and six themes of users' well-being (e.g., mental health factors and value comprehension, mental health and self-care significance, self-awareness, adaptive coping mechanisms, substance use, seeking help and social support). At the same time, the participants noted technical issues, such as bugs and slow loading. The app's role in promoting mental health knowledge and daily motivational reminders received praise, but concerns were raised about repetitive notifications. Users appreciated the mood tracker feature, with suggestions to diversify emotions. Some commended aesthetic appeal and user-friendliness, while others expressed dissatisfaction with the overall user experience. The app's unique ability to act as a reassuring companion was highlighted, but concerns about its generic nature were

noted. Recommendations for improvement include refining notifications and optimizing technical aspects, emphasizing the importance of continuous adaptation based on user feedback for the app's ongoing success and impact.

Conclusion

This study utilized an exploratory mixed-methods approach to qualitatively and quantitatively determine the user satisfaction and content review of the psychology students of Mapua Malayan Colleges Laguna. The study conducted a validated four-point Likert scale questionnaire to gather user satisfaction. Additionally, the study acquired content review and insights through interviews.

In conclusion, the researchers were able to achieve the specific objectives, which include (1) To evaluate the features of the Lusog-Isip app, (2) To determine the user satisfaction level of the Lusog-Isip app among the respondents, (3) To determine the overall satisfaction rate of the respondents of the Lusog-Isip app; (4) To determine the perceptions of the respondents towards the Lusog-Isip mental health app; and (5) To provide recommendations as the foundation of future mental health app features and content development. The satisfaction rate calculation resulted in a 90% CSAT score, which signifies a high overall satisfaction rate.

Additionally, the written interview data provides the respondent's views of the Lusog-Isip app. Some positive features commended by the app users include its evidence-based and reliable content, mood tracker, journal, its availability on smartphones, and its capacity to alleviate stress without the need for professional intervention, thereby resulting in enhanced problem-solving and coping skills among app users.

Furthermore, the participants recommend specific features and content for the Lusog-Isip app's ongoing development and improvement. The possible inclusions suggested by users are comprised of customization settings, interactive games, offline functionality, a comprehensive library of mental health videos and audio resources, supplementary modules and topics for user exploration, an expanded range of mental health helplines, chat feature with friends and mental health experts, a wider mood variety in the mood tracker, and the integration of journal features. Out of six feature classifications, the features under information quality classification (e.g., accuracy, relevance, empirical-based, credibility) received the utmost satisfaction. Likewise, this degree of satisfaction applies to features like data security, data privacy, and accessibility.

Overall, there are still features of Lusog-Isip that require attention and development for future updates and versions of the app, despite how highly the CSAT score rating Lusog-Isip's overall performance based on the psychology students' perception and ratings and how some of the respondents emphasized its strengths. Some of these features fall into categories like aesthetics (e.g., visual appeal), engagement (e.g., interest, entertainment), information quality (e.g., contextual adaptability, concision), and functionality (e.g., accessibility, navigation, performance). Additionally, there is a continued absence of user-suggested updates and certain mental health features that could potentially revolutionize digital mental health implementation in the Philippines (e.g., chat feature with other users, mental health bots or professionals, diverse selection of mood scales, user personalization, interactive modules, social media syncing and sharing feature).

Based on the result of the content review, future researchers may collaborate with other disciplines that specialize in computer science, programming, data analytics, data privacy and even cyber security in the creation of enhanced and updated mental health mobile applications that would be accessible to as many people in need of mental health support.

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